

Managers' Management Skills in in RPO Service Company

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Abstract:

Understanding RPO managers' unique challenges is essential to leading the organization toward excellence. In this premise, this paper analyzed the Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in a highly urbanized city in the National Capital Region during the Calendar Year 2023. A descriptive research design was used in this study. Using a survey questionnaire, the data were collected from 70 respondents of RPO service companies. Results revealed that most of the respondents were younger, male, and single. The study indicates a very high level of managers' conceptual, technical, and human skills. Additionally, there was no significant difference in managers' management skills in an RPO service company regarding conceptual, technical, and human skills when grouped according to age, sex, and civil status. These findings highlight the need for managers to possess a combination of conceptual, technical, and human skills. Managers should think broadly, stay updated with industry trends, and contribute to shaping a positive work culture. These skills will lead to informed decision-making, organizational competitiveness, and effective leadership.

Keywords: RPO managers' challenges, management skills, organizational competitiveness, Negros Occidental

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

In today's dynamic business landscape, marked by globalization, technological advancements, and talent shortages, practical management skills are paramount for organizational success (Mostafiz et al. (2024). Managerial skills encompass a range of abilities and competencies that managers leverage to achieve organizational goals (Asamoah et al., 2021). In the context of recruitment process outsourcing (RPO) service companies, managers must possess hard skills, such as technical proficiency and subject expertise, as well as soft skills, including communication, leadership, and adaptability. These skills drive efficient recruitment processes, ensure client satisfaction, and maintain operational excellence. However, RPO service firm managers frequently need help aligning recruitment strategies with organizational goals, adjusting to market dynamics, and making well-informed decisions. Maintaining strong client relationships and optimizing technical skills and efficiency are ongoing concerns. Despite the recognized importance of managerial skills, empirical studies specifically focused on RPO service companies still need to be expanded.

Therefore, it is imperative to investigate the interplay of conceptual, human, and technical managerial skills in the context of RPO service companies. Besides, successful RPO management requires balancing operational efficiency, strategic alignment, and stakeholder satisfaction. Addressing these key factors can mitigate failure and drive positive outcomes in RPO services to achieve sustainable development (Plamondon, 2023). In this view, the researcher, as an employee of one of the RPO service companies in Manila, has realized that there is a need to determine the level of managers' managerial skills in the organization. Understanding RPO managers' unique challenges is essential to leading the organization toward excellence. It would provide opportunities to gain and improve the researcher's knowledge and skills and be a professional relevant to the job. Hence, this study is conceptualized.

Current State of Knowledge

Knowing how to write a business plan with a cash flow projection, using statistics to analyze data from a market survey, updating software on a computer network, and delivering a persuasive oral presentation are also technical skills. Although initially gained through formal education, technical skills can become quickly outdated. It is essential to nurture and develop them through ongoing learning that takes full advantage of training and job experiences. Human and Interpersonal Skills Recruiters put much emphasis on job candidates' "soft" skills like the ability to communicate, collaborate, and network, to lead and contribute to teams, and to treat others with trust, enthusiasm, and positivity (Schermerhorn et al., 2023). Practical management skills are not inherently inherent and guaranteed in managers. Especially in times of turmoil, managers must remain vigilant and utilize all their

skills and competencies to benefit the organization and its stakeholders, including employees, customers, investors, and the community. In recent years, several highly publicized instances have demonstrated the consequences of managers' failure to effectively apply their skills to meet the challenges of an uncertain and rapidly changing environment (Daft & Marcic, 2022). According to Chamberlin et al. (2018), empowerment is the primary factor explaining why employees perceive high-performance managerial practices as positively impacting job performance. Drawing from social cognitive theory, the authors propose that such practices influence performance by encouraging employees to express their opinions (voice).

Meanwhile, according to Beenen et al. (2021), the Managerial Interpersonal Skills Scale (MIPS) best represents a three-dimensional model comprising supporting, motivating, and managing conflict, collectively indicating a higher-order latent MIPS factor. Their results suggest that the MIPS Scale effectively predicts job attitudes and performance among employees and managers, surpassing personality traits and leader-member exchange. It also constructs closely linked to MIPS, such as social support and conflict management style. A causal interpretation is reinforced by several research designs, including those exploiting new workers joining the firm and workers switching managers. However, people management skills need to improve consistently. Most observed no attrition outcomes. Better people managers themselves receive higher subjective performance ratings, higher promotion rates, and more significant salary increases (Hoffman & Tadelis, 2021).

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine management skills among managers in an RPO service company located in a highly urbanized city in the National Capital Region during the calendar year 2023. Specifically, it aimed to determine: 1) the level of managers' management skills in terms of conceptual, technical, and human or interpersonal skills; 2) the level of management skills when grouped according to these specific areas; and 3) the significant differences in management skills levels when managers are grouped and compared based on these variables.

Research Methodology:

This section discusses the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design, considering the nature of the data involved. In this research, the focus is on an existing phenomenon, the level of managers' management skills in a company, and the researcher opted to use the descriptive research design.

Respondents

Using the Cochran formula, this paper used a stratified random sampling technique to determine the respondents (N=70) out of 85 population.

Procedures for Data Collection

The data for the study was collected using a survey questionnaire. The researcher first wrote a letter to the company's management to conduct a face-to-face survey. After approval was obtained, the researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents. After answering, their responses were compiled and tabulated. The data acquired from the respondents' responses were tallied and tabulated. The data above were processed on a computer using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as a statistical tool to determine the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company;

Objective No. 2 also used a descriptive analytical scheme and mean as a statistical tool to determine the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company when grouped according to age, sex, and income.

Objective No. 3 used a comparative-analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in managers' management skills when grouped according to demographics.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were given utmost importance in the study. The researcher ensured that respondents were free to participate in the study, that their identities were not revealed, and that the data collected would be kept confidential. Voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality, and plagiarism were rigorously enforced.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. Appropriate procedures were followed to give exact data and substantiate solutions to each problem.

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company according to Conceptual, Technical, and Human Skills

Table 1

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Conceptual Skills

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...		
1. creates comprehensive strategies that address various organizational needs.	5.00	Very High Level
2. makes informed decisions based on a deep analysis of complex information.	4.94	Very High Level
3. understands the relationships between different business functions and departments.	4.84	Very High Level
4. forecasts long-term industry trends effectively and their impacts on the organization.	4.89	Very High Level
5. identifies and solves problems that have a broad organizational impact.	4.94	Very High Level
6. encourages and incorporates innovative ideas and approaches in planning.	4.84	Very High Level
7. balances short-term challenges with long-term objectives effectively.	4.94	Very High Level
8. demonstrates an understanding of global trends affecting our industry.	4.89	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.91	Very High Level

Table 1 presents the data on the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in conceptual skills. The overall mean score is 4.91, indicating a very high level of conceptual skills among the managers. The highest mean score is 5.0, interpreted as a very high level in Item No. 1. The lowest mean score is 4.84, interpreted as a very high level, in Item No. 3 and Item No. 6. This implies that managers need to improve their Conceptual skills. Managers with conceptual solid skills can make informed decisions that align with the organization's long-term goals. They can identify trends, anticipate changes, and adapt strategies accordingly. Also, conceptual thinkers can communicate the big picture effectively to their teams. This clarity helps employees understand their roles in achieving organizational objectives.

Table 2

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Technical Skills

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...		
1. uses specialized tools and software effectively required in our work area.	4.90	Very High Level
2. demonstrates a high level of proficiency in industry-specific knowledge.	4.91	Very High Level
3. participates regularly in training or professional development for technical skills.	4.83	Very High Level
4. uses technical knowledge to innovate or improve existing systems and practices.	4.94	Very High Level
5. has a strong understanding of technical processes relevant to your department.	4.80	Very High Level
6. adapts new technologies and integrates them into your work processes quickly.	4.83	Very High Level
7. applies technical skills to improve team productivity and efficiency.	4.81	Very High Level
8. communicates technical information to the team effectively.	4.89	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.87	Very High Level

Table 2 presents the data on the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in technical skills. The overall mean score of the technical skills items is 4.87, indicating a very high level of management skills in technical areas. The highest mean score in this area is 4.94, interpreted as a very high level in Item No. 4. The lowest mean score in Table 4 is 4.80, interpreted as a very high level in Item No. 5, which is

related to managers knowing many skills to manage the team. This implies that managers need to improve their technical skills in managing teams and personnel, which could impact their ability to utilize their technical skills effectively. Managers with strong technical skills can optimize day-to-day operations. Whether it is understanding machinery, software, or industry-specific processes, technical proficiency enhances efficiency.

Table 3
Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Human Skills

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...		
1. manages and resolves conflicts within the team effectively.	4.90	Very High Level
2. motivates and inspires team members consistently	4.94	Very High Level
3. demonstrates active listening and understanding of team members' concerns.	4.89	Very High Level
4. demonstrates empathy and respect for diverse perspectives in the team.	4.93	Very High Level
5. encourages collaborative and inclusive team environment.	4.94	Very High Level
6. provides constructive feedback and support for personal and professional development.	4.94	Very High Level
7. communicates effectively and transparently with the team.	4.89	Very High Level
8. recognizes and appreciates the contributions of team members.	4.91	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.92	Very High Level

Table 3 presents the data on managers' management skills in RPO service companies. The overall mean score of the human skills items is 4.92, indicating a very high level of management skills in an RPO service company in terms of human skills. The highest mean in Table 5 is 4.94, interpreted as a Very high level, in Item Numbers 2, 5, and 6. The lowest mean score in this area is 4.89, interpreted as a very high level in Item Nos. 3 and 7. This implies that it is essential for managers to improve their human skills to foster effective communication within the organization, enable them to make use of human potential, and motivate employees for better results. Trust, respect, and open communication foster a healthy work environment.

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Conceptual, Technical, and Human Skills when grouped according to Age, Sex, and Civil Status

Table 4
Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Conceptual Skills when Grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...				
1. creates comprehensive strategies that address various organizational needs.	5.00	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
2. makes informed decisions based on a deep analysis of complex information.	4.93	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level
3. understands the relationships between different business functions and departments.	4.74	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
4. forecasts long-term industry trends effectively and their impacts on the organization.	4.81	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
5. identifies and solves problems that have a broad organizational impact.	4.98	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
6. encourages and incorporates innovative ideas and approaches in planning.	4.81	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
7. balances short-term challenges with long-term objectives effectively.	4.93	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level
8. demonstrates an understanding of global trends affecting our industry	4.86	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.88	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level

Table 4 shows the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in terms of conceptual skills when grouped according to age. The overall mean of 4.88 for the younger group and 4.96 for the older group signifies a Very High Level of conceptual skills across both age groups. Item 1 has the highest mean of 5.00 for the younger and 5.00 for the older group in item 3 and item 4. The lowest mean scores were 4.74 for the younger group and 4.89 for the older group in item No. 5 and item No. 6, both interpreted as very high levels.

Table 5

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Technical Skills when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager... 1. uses specialized tools and software effectively required in our work area.	4.95	Very High Level	4.82	Very High Level
2. demonstrates a high level of proficiency in industry-specific knowledge.	4.93	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
3. participates regularly in training or professional development for technical skills.	4.81	Very High Level	4.86	Very High Level
4. uses technical knowledge to innovate or improve existing systems and practices.	4.95	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
5. has a strong understanding of technical processes relevant to your department.	4.81	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
6. adapts new technologies and integrates them into your work processes quickly.	4.90	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
7. applies technical skills to improve team productivity and efficiency.	4.83	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
8. communicates technical information to the team effectively.	4.93	Very High Level	4.82	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.89	Very High Level	4.83	Very High Level

Table 5 shows the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in technical skills when grouped according to age. Data shows an overall mean of 4.89 and 4.83 for the younger and older groups, respectively, interpreted as very high technical skills. Interpreted as very high-level Item 1 and Item 4 have the highest mean of 4.95 for the younger group. While for the older group. Item 4 is interpreted as a very high level, with the highest mean being 4.93. Interpreted as very high level, item 3 and Item 5 have the lowest mean of 4.81 for the younger group, and item 6 has the lowest mean of 4.71 for the older group. This implies that managers in an RPO service company with technical skills possess the necessary competencies to handle complex technical challenges and contribute significantly to the company's success.

Table 6

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Human Skills when Grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager... 1. manages and resolves conflicts within the team effectively.	4.90	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
2. motivates and inspires team members consistently	4.98	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
3. demonstrates active listening and understanding of team members' concerns.	4.90	Very High Level	4.86	Very High Level
4. demonstrates empathy and respect for diverse perspectives in the team.	4.90	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level
5. encourages collaborative and inclusive team environment.	4.95	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
6. provides constructive feedback and support for personal and professional development.	4.93	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level
7. communicates effectively and transparently with the team.	4.90	Very High Level	4.86	Very High Level
8. recognizes and appreciates the contributions of team members.	4.93	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level

Overall Mean **4.93** **Very High Level** **4.91** **Very High Level**

Table 6 shows the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in terms of human skills when grouped according to age. An overall mean of 4.93 and 4.91 were generated for the younger and older respondents, respectively, as a very high level of human skills. The highest mean score of 4.98 among the younger group respondents came from item 2 which is interpreted as a very high level. Older group respondents reflected the same high-level interpretation with a mean score of 4.96 in item 4 and item 6. The lowest mean score of 4.90 among the younger respondents came from items 1, 3, 4, and 7. Older group respondents reflected the same very high-level interpretation with a mean score of 4.86 in item No. 3 and in Item No. 7. This implies that the level of managers' management skills in RPO service companies in human skills, when grouped according to age, excel in interpersonal interactions, fostering a positive work culture and employee satisfaction.

Table 7

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Conceptual Skills when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...				
1. creates comprehensive strategies that address various organizational needs.	5.00	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
2. makes informed decisions based on a deep analysis of complex information.	4.92	Very High Level	4.97	Very High Level
3. understands the relationships between different business functions and departments.	4.84	Very High Level	4.85	Very High Level
4. forecasts long-term industry trends effectively and their impacts on the organization.	4.89	Very High Level	4.88	Very High Level
5. identifies and solves problems that have a broad organizational impact.	4.89	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
6. encourages and incorporates innovative ideas and approaches in planning.	4.84	Very High Level	4.85	Very High Level
7. balances short-term challenges with long-term objectives effectively.	4.95	Very High Level	4.94	Very High Level
8. demonstrates an understanding of global trends affecting our industry	4.89	Very High Level	4.88	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.90	Very High Level	4.92	Very High Level

Table 7 shows the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in terms of conceptual skills when grouped according to sex. The overall mean of 4.90 for males and 4.92 for females signifies a very high level of managers' management skills in conceptual skills across both sexes. Item 1 has the highest mean of 5.00 for males and 5.00 for females. The lowest mean scores are 4.84 in males and 4.85 in females in item 3 and item No. 6. This implies that managers have the necessary competencies to drive the organization forward strategically in shaping the company's strategic direction and ensuring its success. These skills include strategic thinking, vision, and problem-solving.

Table 8

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Technical Skills when Grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...				
1. uses specialized tools and software effectively required in our work area.	4.86	Very High Level	4.94	Very High Level
2. demonstrates a high level of proficiency in industry-specific knowledge.	4.86	Very High Level	4.97	Very High Level
3. participates regularly in training or professional development for technical skills.	4.86	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
4. uses technical knowledge to	4.89	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level

innovate or improve existing systems and practices.

5. has a strong understanding of technical processes relevant to your department. 4.78 Very High Level 4.82 Very High Level

6. adapts new technologies and integrates them into your work processes quickly. 4.70 Very High Level 4.97 Very High Level

7. applies technical skills to improve team productivity and efficiency. 4.81 Very High Level 4.82 Very High Level

8. communicates technical information to the team effectively. 4.78 Very High Level 5.00 Very High Level

Overall Mean 4.82 Very High Level 4.91 Very High Level

Table 8 shows the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in technical skills when grouped according to sex. Data shows an overall mean of 4.82 for males and 4.91 for females, interpreted as a very high level of technical skills. Data also shows that males have the highest mean score of 4.89, interpreted as a very high level in item 4. The female has the highest mean score of 5.00, interpreted as very high in Item no. 4 and Item no. 8. The lowest mean score of 4.70, interpreted as a very high level in males, is in item no. 6, while in females, the lowest mean score is 4.79, interpreted as very high level in item 3. This implies that managers of different genders possess the necessary competencies to handle complex technical challenges and contribute significantly to the company's success.

Table 9

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Human Skills when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...				
1. manages and resolves conflicts within the team effectively.	4.95	Very High Level	4.85	Very High Level
2. motivates and inspires team members consistently	4.89	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
3. demonstrates active listening and understanding of team members' concerns.	4.89	Very High Level	4.88	Very High Level
4. demonstrates empathy and respect for diverse perspectives in the team.	4.89	Very High Level	4.97	Very High Level
5. encourages collaborative and inclusive team environment.	4.92	Very High Level	4.97	Very High Level
6. provides constructive feedback and support for personal and professional development.	4.97	Very High Level	4.91	Very High Level
7. communicates effectively and transparently with the team.	4.95	Very High Level	4.82	Very High Level
8. recognizes and appreciates the contributions of team members.	4.92	Very High Level	4.91	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.92	Very High Level	4.91	Very High Level

Table 9 shows the managers' management skills level regarding human skills in an RPO service company when grouped according to sex. Data shows an overall mean of 4.92 for males and 4.91 for females, interpreted as a very high level of human skills. Data also indicates that Male has the highest mean score of 4.89, interpreted as a very high level in Item No. 4. Females have the highest mean score of 5.00, interpreted as a very high level in Item No. 4, and Item No. 8. The lowest mean score of 4.70, interpreted as a very high level in males, is in item no. 6, while in females, the lowest mean score is 4.79, interpreted as very high level in item 3. This implies that managers of different genders excel in interpersonal interactions, fostering a positive work culture and employee satisfaction.

Table 10

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Conceptual Skills when Grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...				
1. creates comprehensive strategies that address various organizational needs.	5.00	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
2. makes informed decisions based	4.91	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level

on a deep analysis of complex information.

3. understands the relationships between different business functions and departments.	4.84	Very High Level	4.85	Very High Level
4. forecasts long-term industry trends effectively and their impacts on the organization.	4.88	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
5. identifies and solves problems that have a broad organizational impact.	4.95	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
6. encourages and incorporates innovative ideas and approaches in planning.	4.81	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
7. balances short-term challenges with long-term objectives effectively.	4.93	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level
8. demonstrates an understanding of global trends affecting our industry	4.88	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.90	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level

Table 10 shows the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in terms of conceptual skills when grouped according to civil status. Data shows an overall mean of 4.90 for single group respondents and 4.93 for married group respondents, which is interpreted as a very high level of managerial skills in conceptual skills. Data also shows that for single-group respondents, the highest mean score is 5.00, interpreted as a very high level in Item No. 1. For married group respondents, the highest mean score is 5.00, item No. 1 and item No. 2. The female has the highest mean score of 5.00, which is interpreted as a very high level in Item no. 4 and Item no. 8. The lowest mean score of 4.81 is also interpreted as a very high level for the single group, is item no. 6, while in the married group, the lowest mean score is 4.85 interpreted as Very High Level in item 3. This implies that managers excel in developing strategies that address organizational needs and can make informed decisions based on deep analysis.

Table 11

Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Technical Skills when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...				
1. uses specialized tools and software effectively required in our work area.	4.84	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
2. demonstrates a high level of proficiency in industry-specific knowledge.	4.86	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
3. participates regularly in training or professional development for technical skills.	4.79	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
4. uses technical knowledge to innovate or improve existing systems and practices.	4.95	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
5. has a strong understanding of technical processes relevant to your department.	4.84	Very High Level	4.74	Very High Level
6. adapts new technologies and integrates them into your work processes quickly.	4.79	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
7. applies technical skills to improve team productivity and efficiency.	4.84	Very High Level	4.78	Very High Level
8. communicates technical information to the team effectively.	4.84	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.84	Very High Level	4.90	Very High Level

Table 11 shows the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in technical skills when grouped according to civil status. Data shows an overall mean of 4.84 for single and 4.90 for married, interpreted as a very high level of technical skills. Achieving a perfect score of 5.00 (item no. 2) emphasizes their deep knowledge in the relevant field, and likewise, achieving a perfect score of 5.00 (item no. 1) showcases their adeptness in utilizing technical tools effectively. Data also shows that the married group of respondents has the highest mean score of 5.00 (item no. 1), interpreted as Very High Level, showcasing the manager's management skills in utilizing technical tools effectively, and also in Item no. 2, Achieving a perfect score of 5.00, emphasizing managers deep knowledge in the relevant field. The lowest mean score of 4.74 is interpreted as a very high level in the married group in item 5, which states that they strongly understand technical processes relevant to the department. This implies that managers possess the necessary competencies to handle complex technical challenges and contribute significantly to the company's success.

Table 12
Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Human Skills when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As an employee, my manager...				
1. manages and resolves conflicts within the team effectively.	4.86	Very High Level	4.96	Very High Level
2. motivates and inspires team members consistently	4.95	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
3. demonstrates active listening and understanding of team members' concerns.	4.88	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
4. demonstrates empathy and respects diverse perspectives in the team.	4.93	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
5. encourages collaborative and inclusive team environment.	4.91	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
6. provides constructive feedback and support for personal and professional development.	4.95	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
7. communicates effectively and transparently with the team.	4.86	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level
8. recognizes and appreciates the contributions of team members.	4.93	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.91	Very High Level	4.93	Very High Level

Table 12 shows the managers' level of management skills in an RPO service company in terms of human skills when grouped according to civil status. An overall mean of 4.91 and 4.93 were generated for single and married respondents, respectively, interpreted as a Very High Level of managers' managerial skills in human skills. Managers with solid human skills can build cohesive teams. They understand team dynamics, encourage collaboration, and create an inclusive work environment. The highest mean score of 5.00 among the married group respondents came from item 5. The lowest mean score of 4.86 among the single-group respondents came from items 1 and 7.

Comparative Analysis of the Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Conceptual, Technical, and Human Skills when Grouped according to Demographics

Table 13
Difference in the Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Conceptual Skills when grouped and compared according to Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	42	32.35	455.500	0.056		Not Significant
	Older	28	40.23				
Sex	Male	37	36.31	580.500	0.672	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	33	34.59				
Civil Status	Single	43	33.34	487.500	0.178		Not Significant

Married 27 38.94

Table 13 presents the differences in the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in terms of conceptual skills when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and civil status, using the Mann-Whitney U-test. As gleaned in the table, the computed mean rank in terms of age is 32.35 for younger employees and 40.23 for older employees, with a p-value of 0.056, which is interpreted as insignificant. In terms of sex, the computed mean rank of the male group is 36.31, while for the female group, the mean rank is 34.59, with a p-value of 0.672, which is interpreted as not significant. Regarding Civil Status, the mean ranks for single and married employees are 33.34 and 38.94, respectively, with no significant difference between the two groups (p=0.178). This indicates that sex is also not a significant factor in determining the level of managers' managerial skills in conceptual skills. Hence, when the employees are grouped according to age, sex, and civil status, the p-values are more significant than 0.05, interpreted as insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis states, "There is no significant difference in the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in conceptual skills when grouped and compared according to variables."

Table 14

Difference in the Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Technical Skills when grouped according to Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	42	36.83	532.000	0.461		Not Significant
	Older	28	33.50				
Sex	Male	37	32.39	495.500	0.138	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	33	38.98				
Civil Status	Single	43	34.34	530.500	0.508		Not Significant
	Married	27	37.35				

Table 14 presents the differences in the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company regarding technical skills when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and civil status, using the Mann-Whitney U-test. As gleaned in the table, the computed mean rank in terms of age is 36.83 for younger employees and 33.50 for older employees, with a p-value of 0.461, which is interpreted as insignificant. In terms of sex, the computed mean rank of the male group is 32.39, while for the female group, the mean rank is 38.98 with a p-value of 0.138, which is interpreted as not significant. Regarding civil status, the mean ranks for single and married employees are 34.34 and 37.35, respectively, with no significant difference between the two groups (p=0.508). This indicates that sex is also not a significant factor in determining the level of managers' managerial skills in technical skills. Hence, when the employees are grouped according to age, sex, and civil status, the p-values are more significant than 0.05, interpreted as insignificant. Therefore, when grouped and compared according to variables, the null hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the level of managers' management skills in RPO service company in technical skills," is accepted.

Table 15

Difference in the Level of Managers' Management Skills in an RPO Service Company in Human Skills when Grouped according to Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	42	36.35	552.500	0.621		Not Significant
	Older	28	34.23				
Sex	Male	37	35.62	606.000	0.951	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	33	35.36				
Civil Status	Single	43	34.19	524.000	0.428		Not Significant
	Married	27	37.59				

Table 15 presents the differences in the level of managers' management skills in an RPO service company in terms of human skills when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and civil status, using the Mann-Whitney U-test. As gleaned in the table, the computed mean rank in terms of age is 36.35 for younger employees and 34.23 for older employees, with a p-value of 0.621, which is interpreted as insignificant. In terms of sex, the computed mean rank of the male group is 35.62, while for the female group, the mean rank is 35.36 with a p-value of 0.951, which is interpreted as not significant. Regarding civil status, the mean ranks for single and married employees are 34.19 and 37.59, respectively, with no significant difference between the two groups ($p=0.428$). This indicates that sex is also not a significant factor in determining the level of managers' managerial skills in human skills. Hence, when the employees are grouped according to age, sex, and civil status, the p-values are more excellent than 0.05, which is interpreted as insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis states, "There is no significant difference in the level of managers' management skills in RPO service companies regarding human skills when grouped and compared according to variables."

Conclusion

In conclusion, all results highlighted the very high level of managers' management skills under these categories: conceptual, technical, and human skills in an RPO service company. However, we must re-think the accepted ideas in the changing global landscape to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage. These findings highlight the need for managers to possess a combination of conceptual, technical, and human skills. Managers should think broadly, stay updated with industry trends, and contribute to shaping a positive work culture. Developing these skills will lead to informed decision-making, organizational competitiveness, and effective leadership.

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